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Research paper

Stream function-vorticity formulation for two-dimensional turbulent flows

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ABSTRACT

The stream function-vorticity formulation is often employed to determine two-dimensional flow fields because the introduction of the stream function avoids considering continuity equation and evaluating the pressure field. This study discusses an alternative and simplified formulation of the average vorticity equation, which introduces the turbulent vorticity diffusivity, \mathcal{D}_T , and assumes that \mathcal{D}_T is linearly related to the eddy viscosity, ν_T ($\mathcal{D}_T = C\nu_T$). The hydrodynamic problem is closed by means of a two-equation turbulence model and the differences between the alternative formulation and the complete version of vorticity equation are discussed by applying the two different formulations to study the turbulent boundary layer generated by an oscillatory and uniform pressure gradient. The influence of the Reynolds number, dimensionless bottom roughness and constant C is investigated. The results show that the simplified vorticity equation leads to erroneous results that significantly differ from those obtained by considering the complete equation, even if the value of the eddy diffusivity is tuned to minimize the differences. Therefore, it is suggested to consider the full averaged vorticity equation even if more computational resources are required.

Keywords: Turbulent flow, $\psi - \omega$ formulation, bottom boundary layer, eddy viscosity, Reynolds equations

1 Introduction

The vorticity-stream function formulation is a useful approach to solve two-dimensional unsteady flow problems when considering an incompressible fluid. The flow over a backward/forward facing step, the driven cavity flow, the unsteady flow around a cylinder or an array of cylinders, the dynamics of the two-dimensional vortices generated in a Taylor-Couette flow of finite extent are just a few examples of the problems which can be efficiently solved by using the vorticity-stream function formulation (Ambethkar and Kumar, 2017; Kotovshchikova and Lui, 2011; Lopez, Pedraza and Toro, 2017; Loukopoulos, Katsiaris and Karahalios, 2003; Poochinapan, 2012; Ray and Kalita, 2016; Yu and Tian, 2013). Indeed, for a two-dimensional incompressible flow, the stream function ψ can be introduced to satisfy the incompressibility constraint and the Navier-Stokes equations can be transformed into a fourth-order nonlinear partial differential equation. Then, by introducing the vorticity ω , this single equation can be separated into two second-order partial differential equations, the unknowns of which are the stream function and the vorticity. This approach is known as the stream-vorticity formulation and avoids the difficulties associated with solving pressure equation of the conventional velocity–pressure formulations of the Navier–Stokes equations.

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By introducing a Cartesian coordinate system (x, y) and the stream function, ψ , such that the two velocity components u and v are simply

$$u = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y} \quad \text{and} \quad v = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x}, \quad (1)$$

continuity equation is identically satisfied and the two components of momentum equation can be combined to provide the vorticity equation:

$$\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\nu \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\nu \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} \right) = \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial y^2} \right) \quad (2)$$

where ν is the kinematic viscosity of the fluid and the vorticity turns out to be $\omega = -\left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2}\right)$. Therefore, the time development of the flow field can be computed by mean of Eq. (2) and the subsequent use of

$$\omega = -\left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

which allows to evaluate the stream function ψ and, hence, the velocity field by means of Eq. (1).

A similar approach can be used to determine the average flow if the turbulent regime is considered. However, even introducing the Boussinesq assumption and modelling the turbulent stresses by means of the eddy viscosity, ν_T , the vorticity equation becomes more complex than Eq. (2) with $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\nu \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\nu \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} \right)$ simply replaced by $\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[(\nu + \nu_T) \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[(\nu + \nu_T) \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} \right]$. Indeed, the eddy viscosity depends on the two spatial coordinates x and y and the vorticity equation turns out to be (see Chien (1979)):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} &= \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial y^2} \right) + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \left[\nu_T \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) \right] + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} \left(2\nu_T \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) \\ &\quad - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial y} \left(2\nu_T \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \left[\nu_T \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) \right] = \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial y^2} \right) + \frac{\partial^2 \nu_T}{\partial x^2} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) \\ &\quad + \nu_T \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) + 2 \frac{\partial \nu_T}{\partial x} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) - \frac{\partial^2 \nu_T}{\partial y^2} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) - \nu_T \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) \\ &\quad - 2 \frac{\partial \nu_T}{\partial y} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) + 2 \frac{\partial^2 \nu_T}{\partial x \partial y} \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) + 2 \frac{\partial \nu_T}{\partial y} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) + 2 \frac{\partial \nu_T}{\partial x} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) \\ &\quad + 2\nu_T \left(\frac{\partial^3 v}{\partial x \partial y^2} - \frac{\partial^3 u}{\partial x^2 \partial y} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

An alternative and simplified formulation of the vorticity equation in a turbulent flow might be

$$\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[(\nu + \mathcal{D}_T) \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} \right] + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[(\nu + \mathcal{D}_T) \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} \right] \quad (5)$$

where \mathcal{D}_T is the ‘‘turbulent diffusivity’’ of the average vorticity.

Even though an appropriate modelling of turbulence dynamics and the use of Eq. (4) allow to obtain a reliable solution of momentum and continuity equations in a two-dimensional domain, one of the main weaknesses of this approach is the computational resources that the complete vorticity equation (Eq. 4) requires. If similar results were achieved with the alternative formulation and an appropriate choice of \mathcal{D}_T , the computational and problem-solving time would be significantly reduced. In this contribution, we provide an answer to the following questions: (1) what is the most appropriate value of \mathcal{D}_T in the alternative and simplified formulation? (2) is it possible to

determine a constant C such that \mathcal{D}_T is equal $C\nu_T$ or, in other words, does a Schmidt number for vorticity exists?

The paper is structured as follows: the hydrodynamic problem is outlined in Section 2 by considering a specific problem: the oscillatory boundary layer generated close to a wall by the harmonic oscillations of a fluid. Turbulence is described by introducing the two-equation turbulence model of Menter, Kuntz and Langtry (2003). The numerical approach used to determine the flow field and the validation of the turbulence model are presented in Section 3. Section 4 provides the results obtained by the alternative turbulent vorticity equation focusing on minimizing the differences with the complete equation. Finally, the conclusions are summarized in Section 5.

2 The problem

The stream function-vorticity formulation is used to study the turbulent boundary layer generated close to a fixed wall by the harmonic oscillations of a viscous fluid. A Cartesian coordinate system is introduced with the (x, z) -plane coincident with the fixed wall, the x -axis aligned with the fluid oscillation and the y -axis orthogonal to the wall. Hence, the average velocity components are denoted as (u, v, w) and, far from the wall, the fluid velocity u_∞ is described by

$$u_\infty = U_0 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi t}{T}\right) \quad (6)$$

where U_0 and T are the amplitude and period of the velocity oscillations.

If the average flow is assumed to be uniform along the x - and z -axes, the only non-vanishing velocity component u of the average velocity is the solution of the following equation

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial u_\infty}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[(\nu + \nu_T) \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right] \quad (7)$$

where the turbulent stresses are evaluated by introducing the Boussinesq assumption (Boussinesq, 1987) and the turbulent eddy viscosity, ν_T . The pressure gradient $\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = -\rho \frac{\partial u_\infty}{\partial t}$ is the forcing term that drives the fluid oscillations.

The solution of Eq. (7) can be easily determined by a numerical approach once a turbulence model is introduced to evaluate the turbulent eddy viscosity ν_T . In Blondeaux, Vittori and Porcile (2018), the problem is solved by introducing different turbulence models and the results are compared with experimental measurements to quantify the accuracy of modelling the Reynolds stresses by a two-equation turbulence model.

Hereinafter, Menter's turbulence model (Menter, 1994; Menter et al., 2003) is used since this model is largely employed and it can be applied within the region closest to a wall thus forcing the vanishing of both the velocity and the turbulent kinetic energy at the bottom. Moreover, Díaz-Carrasco, Vittori, Blondeaux and Ortega-Sánchez (2019) showed that the turbulence model of Menter et al. (2003) properly describes the turbulent flow structure and the sediment transport in suspension generated by propagating sea waves both close to the bed (boundary layer) and far from it.

As described in Blondeaux et al. (2018) and Díaz-Carrasco et al. (2019), Menter's turbulence model consists of the original $k - \Omega$ model by Wilcox (1988) in the inner region of the boundary layer and switches to the standard $k - \epsilon$ model (Jones and Launder, 1972) in the outer region. The blending between the two models is obtained by using a blending function $F_1(y)$, which changes gradually from 1 to 0 moving from the inner region to the outer region. Presently, the SST-V2003

version of the model is used. In the present case, the equations for k and Ω are:

$$\frac{\partial k}{\partial t} = \tilde{P}_k - \beta_k \Omega k + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[(\nu + \nu_T \sigma_k) \frac{\partial k}{\partial y} \right] \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial t} = \gamma \frac{\tilde{P}_k}{\nu_T} - \beta_\Omega \Omega^2 + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[(\nu + \nu_T \sigma_\Omega) \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial y} \right] + 2(1 - F_1) \sigma_{\Omega 2} \frac{1}{\Omega} \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial y} \frac{\partial k}{\partial y} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\nu_T = \min \left(\frac{k}{\Omega}, \frac{a_1 k}{DF_2} \right) \quad (10)$$

and D is an invariant measure of the strain rate tensor provided by $D = |\partial u / \partial y|$. Moreover, $F_2 = \tanh [(\arg_2)^2]$ with $\arg_2 = \max \left(\frac{2\sqrt{k}}{\beta_k \Omega y}, \frac{500\nu}{\Omega y^2} \right)$ and the production term makes use of the limiter \tilde{P}_k defined by $\tilde{P}_k = \min \left(\nu_T \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right)^2, 10\beta_k \Omega k \right)$ that prevents the build-up of turbulence in stagnation regions. The values of the constants of the model are determined by using the blending function F_1 . If λ_1 is the value of the generic constant in the original $k - \Omega$ model and λ_2 is the value of the corresponding constant in the transformed $k - \epsilon$ model, the value λ to be used in the SST-V2003 model is:

$$\lambda = F_1 \lambda_1 + (1 - F_1) \lambda_2 \quad (11)$$

where the blending function F_1 is defined by $F_1 = \tanh [(\arg_1)^4]$ with $\arg_1 = \min \left[\max \left(\frac{\sqrt{k}}{\beta_k \Omega y}, \frac{500\nu}{y^2 \Omega} \right); \frac{4\sigma_{\Omega 2} k}{CD_{k\Omega} y^2} \right]$ and $CD_{k\Omega} = \max \left(2\sigma_{\Omega 2} \frac{1}{\Omega} \frac{\partial k}{\partial y} \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial y}, 10^{-10} \right)$

The values of the constants in the original $k - \Omega$ and in the transformed $k - \epsilon$ model are gathered in Table 1.

Turbulence model	σ_Ω	σ_k	β_Ω	β_k	γ
Wilcox model	0.5	0.85	0.075	0.9	0.556
$k - \epsilon$ model	0.856	1	0.0828	5/9	0.44

Table 1 Parameter set up for the turbulence model of Menter et al. (2003).

The boundary conditions which should be forced at the wall for k and Ω are the same as those used in the $k - \Omega$ model (see Blondeaux et al. (2018)):

$$u = 0, \quad k = 0, \quad \Omega = \frac{\tau_w}{\mu} S(k_s^+) \quad \text{at } y = 0 \quad (12)$$

where τ_w is the bottom shear stress and k_s^+ is equal to $\frac{k_s u_\tau}{\nu}$, k_s being the bottom roughness and $u_\tau = \sqrt{\tau_w / \rho}$ the shear velocity. The function S is provided by Wilcox (1988):

$$S = 625 \quad \text{if } k_s^+ < 1; \quad S = \left(\frac{50}{k_s^+} \right)^2 \quad \text{if } 1 \leq k_s^+ < 25; \quad S = \frac{100}{k_s^+} \quad \text{if } k_s^+ \geq 25 \quad (13)$$

Even though the solution of the problem just formulated can be easily found by means of the numerical integration of Eq. (7) along with the integration of the equations of the turbulence model (Díaz-Carrasco et al., 2019), hereinafter, the problem is solved by using the $\psi - \omega$ formulation to provide an answer to the question described in the Introduction. In particular, attention is focused on the vorticity field which is obtained, first, by integrating

$$\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial t} = (\nu + \nu_T) \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \nu_T}{\partial y^2} \omega + 2 \frac{\partial \nu_T}{\partial y} \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} \quad (14)$$

which comes from Eq. (4). Then, following the alternative formulation (Eq. 5), the “turbulent vorticity diffusivity”, \mathcal{D}_T is introduced such that: $\langle \omega' u' \rangle = \mathcal{D}_T \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x}$ and $\langle \omega' v' \rangle = \mathcal{D}_T \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y}$ (where $\langle X \rangle$ denotes the Reynolds averaged value of X), and the following equation is solved

$$\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial t} = (\nu + \mathcal{D}_T) \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial \mathcal{D}_T}{\partial y} \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} \quad (15)$$

Of course, \mathcal{D}_T has to be determined in order to close the problem.

Even though simple algebra shows that \mathcal{D}_T cannot be proportional to ν_T , we assume that $\mathcal{D}_T = \mathcal{C} \nu_T$, \mathcal{C} being the inverse of a kind of Schmidt number. Hence, the idea is to identify the value of \mathcal{C} that provides the best and acceptable results. First, Eq. (15) is integrated by taking $\mathcal{C} = 1$ and the difference between these results and those obtained by means of Eq. (14) are evaluated. Then, further results are obtained with different values of \mathcal{C} in order to determine which is the value that minimizes the differences between the results provided by Eq. (14) and those obtained by means of Eq. (15). The differences are determined as function of y and t to verify whether they are small everywhere and at any phase of the oscillatory cycle. Moreover, we want to check if the alternative formulation provides a reasonable description of the phenomenon or not. This procedure is heuristic but the use of Eq. (5) would save a lot of computational time, especially when curvilinear coordinates or a coordinate stretching are introduced (Chien, 1979).

Finally, in both cases (Eq. 14 and Eq. 15), the velocity is obtained from

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\omega \quad (16)$$

along with the boundary condition which enforces the vanishing of the velocity at the wall and the matching with the oscillating fluid far from the wall.

3 Numerical solution and validation

The solution of the hydrodynamic problem depends on two parameters, namely the Reynolds number, $R_\delta = \frac{U_0 \delta}{\nu}$, defined using the thickness $\delta = \sqrt{\frac{\nu T}{\pi}}$ of the Stokes boundary layer (being T the period of the oscillations), and the dimensionless bottom roughness, $\frac{k_s}{\delta}$. Alternatively, it is possible to use the Reynolds number $Re = \frac{U_0 a}{\nu}$ defined using the amplitude a of the fluid displacement oscillations ($a = \frac{U_0 T}{2\pi}$) and the dimensionless roughness, $\frac{k_s}{a}$. Simple algebra shows that: $Re = \frac{R_\delta^2}{2}$ and $\frac{k_s}{a} = \frac{k_s}{\delta} \frac{2}{R_\delta}$. Following this dimensional analysis, the results are presented for different values of R_δ and k_s/δ .

The hydrodynamic problem is solved numerically by means of the following finite difference approach: (i) a standard centred second-order finite difference approximation is employed to approximate the spatial derivatives along the y -direction, and (ii) the temporal derivatives are approximated by means of the second order Runge-Kutta method. In order to increase the accuracy of

Figure 1 Velocity profile in a Stokes boundary layer at different phases of the oscillation cycle: comparison between model predictions obtained with Menter et al. (2003)'s turbulence model and the experimental measurements of Jensen et al. (1989). (Top panel): test n. 10, $R_\delta = 3464$, smooth wall. (Bottom panel) test n. 13, $R_\delta = 3464$, rough wall ($z^* = 0.47$ mm).

the numerical results, the grid points are denser close to the bottom, where the velocity and the vorticity gradients are large. The dimensionless time step, Δt , is chosen of order $10^{-6}T$ to keep the calculations stable. Finally, the initial condition of velocity is set to zero, and very small initial values are given to k and Ω , to avoid problems of numerical instability. The simulations are carried out till a periodic flow is attained.

Fig. 1 shows a comparison between the model results obtained by integrating Eq. (7) and the measurements of two experiments of Jensen et al. (1989) which are characterized by a value of $R_\delta = 3464$ and two different values of the wall roughness. In the top panel a smooth wall is considered while in the bottom panel the value of $\frac{k_s}{\delta}$ is equal to 0.47. Looking at Fig. 1 and at the results described in Blondeaux et al. (2018) and in Díaz-Carrasco et al. (2019), it can be concluded that the turbulence model of Menter (Menter et al., 2003) provides acceptable results. Indeed, a fair agreement between the model results and the experimental measurements can be observed and the differences cannot be ascribed only to deficiencies of the turbulence model and/or errors of the numerical approach since the measurements of the velocity far from the wall at $\phi = -30^\circ$ and $\phi = -60^\circ$ should be equal to the measurements at $\phi = 30^\circ$ and $\phi = 60^\circ$, respectively, whereas

significant differences can be observed.

4 The alternative turbulent vorticity equation

First of all, it is worth pointing out that the results obtained by integrating Eq. (7) are indistinguishable from those provided by Eq. (14), since the solution of the hydrodynamic problem obtained by considering momentum equation cannot be different from that provided by vorticity equation. Hence, in the following the results obtained by integrating Eq. (14), i.e. the complete vorticity equation, are compared with those obtained by integrating the alternative and simplified version of the vorticity equation, i.e. Eq. (15).

Figure 2 Velocity profiles in a Stokes boundary layer at different phases of the oscillation cycle for $R_\delta = 750$ and $k_s/\delta = 0.01$ (the velocity profiles are plotted for $t = (\frac{1}{4} + \frac{n}{10})T +$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 9$) Continuous line = complete vorticity equation (Eq. 14), broken line = simplified vorticity equation (Eq. 15) with $C = 1.0$.

Fig. 2 shows the velocity profile $u(y, t)$ for a moderate value of the Reynolds number, R_δ , and a small value of the wall roughness such that the wall can be considered smooth from a hydrodynamic point of view ($R_\delta = 750$, $\frac{k_s}{\delta} = 0.01$). For such values of the parameters the flow becomes turbulent when the free stream velocity is maximum and keeps turbulent during the decelerating phases of the cycle but it relaminarizes during the accelerating phases (Blondeaux et al., 2018). In Fig. 2, the velocity is plotted versus y at different phases of the cycle. The figure clearly shows that the results provided by Eq. (15) with $C = 1.0$ are characterized by a velocity overshoot which is observed for values of y much larger than those of the correct solution obtained by integrating Eq. (14).

The differences between the results provided by Eq. (14) and those obtained by means of Eq. (15) are significant and they might be attributed to the moderate value of the Reynolds number such that turbulence intensity is significant only during a part of the oscillation cycle but the flow relaminarizes during the other part of the cycle. Hence, the next step was to increase the Reynolds number to achieve a fully turbulent flow. However, the differences of the results obtained by means of Eqs. (14) and (15) with $C = 1.0$ keep significant also considering larger values of the Reynolds number as it appears looking at Fig. 3, where the Reynolds number is equal to 1500 (the roughness size is equal to $\frac{k_s}{\delta} = 0.01$ both in Fig. 2 and 3). Indeed, even though the flow regime is turbulent for almost the whole cycle when R_δ is equal to 1500, the differences between the results provided by the full vorticity equation and the simplified one do not decrease.

Also the roughness size might affect the model results. Hence, the model results are compared with those provided by the Reynolds equation for a rough wall. Fig. 4 shows the velocity profiles

Figure 3 Velocity profiles in a Stokes boundary layer at different phases of the oscillation cycle for $R_\delta = 1500$ and $k_s/\delta = 0.01$ (the velocity profiles are plotted for $t = (\frac{1}{4} + \frac{n}{10})T+$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 9$). Continuous line = complete vorticity equation (Eq. 14), broken line = simplified vorticity equation (Eq. 15) with $C = 1.0$.

for $R_\delta = 1500$ and $\frac{k_s}{\delta} = 1.0$, that is, for a roughness size equal to the thickness of the boundary layer. The results plotted in Fig. 4 shows that the performance of the model does not improve when the roughness size is increased and the simplified vorticity equation with $C = 1.0$ fails to describe the vorticity dynamics.

Figure 4 Velocity profiles in a Stokes boundary layer at different phases of the oscillation cycle for $R_\delta = 1500$ and $k_s/\delta = 1.0$ (the velocity profiles are plotted for $t = (\frac{1}{4} + \frac{n}{10})T+$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 9$). Continuous line = complete vorticity equation (Eq. 14), broken line = simplified vorticity equation (Eq. 15) with $C = 1.0$.

As pointed out previously, Eq. (15) might describe vorticity dynamics if a proper value of \mathcal{D}_T is chosen. Hence, further results have been obtained by varying the value of the constant C , i.e. varying the Schmidt number of the phenomenon to possibly find the value which minimizes the differences between the actual solution and the approximate solution. Fig. 5 shows the velocity profile for $R_\delta = 1500$, $\frac{k_s}{\delta} = 1.0$ and four different values of C , namely 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 1.0.

The results improve by decreasing the value of the constant C and the better agreement is found for C falling between 0.1 and 0.2. However, the overshooting of the velocity profile predicted by the simplified model is too large when compared with the correct results obtained either with

Figure 5 Velocity profiles in a Stokes boundary layer at different phases of the oscillation cycle for $R_\delta = 1500$ and $k_s/\delta = 1.0$ (the velocity profiles are plotted for $t = (\frac{1}{4} + \frac{n}{10})T$ and $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 9$). Thin line = complete vorticity equation (Eq. 14), thick line = simplified vorticity equation (Eq. 15). (Top left panel) $C = 1.0$; (top right panel) $C = 0.4$; (bottom left panel) $C = 0.2$; (bottom right panel) $C = 0.1$;

momentum equation or the correct vorticity equation.

The failure of using Eq. (15) to describe vorticity dynamics might be ascribed at the particular turbulence model used to quantify the eddy viscosity. However, the qualitative behaviour of the results of the two approaches does not change when a different turbulence model is employed to describe turbulence dynamics. The reader interested to the effects of different turbulence models on the computed flow field is referred to Blondeaux et al. (2018).

5 Conclusion

This paper discusses the use of an alternative formulation of the average vorticity equation to determine a two-dimensional turbulent flow field. Instead of using the complete equation obtained by applying the curl operator to the Reynolds averaged momentum equations, where the Reynolds stresses are evaluated by means of the Boussinesq assumption and the turbulent eddy viscosity ν_T , in this work the turbulent vorticity diffusivity, \mathcal{D}_T , is introduced and \mathcal{D}_T is assumed to be proportional to the eddy viscosity ($\mathcal{D}_T \sim \nu_T$). The obtained results show that only the complete version of the averaged vorticity equation provides a reliable description of the flow field and its use is recommended even it requires more computational resources, in particular when curvilinear coordinate systems are used and/or the geometry under investigation asks for a coordinate stretching.

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Turbulence model	σ_{Ω}	σ_k	β_{Ω}	β_k	γ
Wilcox model	0.5	0.85	0.075	0.9	0.556
$k-\varepsilon$ model	0.856	1	0.0828	5/9	0.44

Table 1 Parameter set up for the turbulence model of Menter et al. (2003).

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